
Paper: Watching people decide: decision prediction using heatmaps of reading a decision-support document.

Sucheta Ghosh^{1,*}, Pamela Wronski², Jan Koetsenruijter², Wolfgang Mueller¹, Michel Wensing²

**1 Scientific Databases & Visualization Group (SDBV), Heidelberg
Institute for Theoretical Studies – HITS gGmbH,**

Schloss-Wolfsbrunnenweg 35, 69118, Heidelberg, Germany

**2 Department of General Practice and Health Services Research,
Heidelberg University Hospital, Im Neuenheimer Feld 130.3, 69120,
Heidelberg, Germany**

* sucheta.ghosh@h-its.org

Abstract

Previous studies show that reading behavior varies with the readers' Levels of Expertise (LoE) in a task area. Except for LoE, other factors like acquired information plays a role in this process. In the area of health policymaking, people read supporting documents to inform their decisions. This leads to a natural question: could it be possible to predict the decisions based on the reading pattern of the supporting document on top of their LoE? In this work we found that reading patterns could be useful for forecasting a decision, given the LoE of the individual. Heatmaps can be used as both qualitative and quantitative measures for reading patterns. For full abstract see the reference (<https://doi.org/10.1167/jov.21.9.2631>) [46].

Introduction

Reading is a method of systematic examination and comprehension of a document. Through the process of reading people create and/or optimize the mental models. A mental model or mental representation is a kind of internal symbol or representation of external reality, hypothesized to play a major role in cognition, reasoning and decision-making [1]. There is significant difference of mental models of people according to the levels of expertise [2,3,4]. The difference may influence the speed of making decision or maybe even the decisions itself. Other studies have already shown [2], that both experts and novices need supporting documents to inform on and decide on policies. The leading health organizations around the world, including the World Health Organization, have recognized the need to use more rigorous processes to ensure that health policy decisions are informed by the best available research evidence [5, 6]. This, however, does not take away the fact that there still is a difference in decision making by experts, and novices [7, 8]. Thus, it is known that here exists a relationship between the Level of Expertise (LoE) of an individual and the decision made by that individual [7]. Now we want to explore: is there any connection between the patterns of reading and the decisions made? Is it possible to observe the correlation among the levels of expertise of the individuals and the decisions made by them? And/or can we even

predict the decision given the patterns of reading of an individual? We attempt to answer these questions using eye tracker data. The eye tracker data was collected when several participants read a supporting document during a health policy decision making task. Here the patterns of reading can be well implied to the characteristics found by an eye tracker. So, the aim of this work is to understand whether we can predict the decision of a policymaking task, using the reading patterns captured by an eye tracker. In this study, we collected eye tracker data of the reading of the individual before making decision on the policies. Then we acquired the heatmap images from the eye tracker data. We used the heatmap images to compute and visualize the correlations of the reading patterns of the individuals. Then we utilize the correlation values as a basis for the prediction of the decision made by the participants in the task. To accomplish this, we extract heatmaps of the reading of the participants of our experiment, using average fixation duration. First, (1) we performed the prediction through post-hoc cluster analysis, to observe the outcome when we take account the reading pattern as a singular characteristic, then (2) we ensemble the reading patterns and other possible features like LoE and pupillometric data to predict the decision using regression analysis. The main contribution of this paper is to use the heatmap image as a source to compute and discuss the correlation, and then to use this as the feature to predict the decision with the feature-ensemble. The paper is oriented as follows : first we introduce the problem in the section 1. Then we describe the background of the work at section 1.1. Then at the section 2, we elaborate on the data collection with a glimpse of data analysis of the priors, then we describe the method used in this paper in section 2.2. Next, we illustrate the results at the section 3. In the section 4 we discuss the result. Finally, at the section 5 we conclude our findings.

Background

Decision-making process is a reasoning process that is guided by values, preferences, and beliefs of the decision-maker [9]. Decisions under uncertainty are made through analysis of known and unknown variables which should lead to the best probabilistic decision [10, 11]. Ultimately, all these decisions are meant to prompt to the future benefit to someone or something. These involve choices like whether to implement policy A or B, etc. Without the intrinsic uncertainty in these, the decisions would be simple and easily predictable. However, we observe that for many decisions the uncertainty probabilities cannot be known or estimated, when we follow the definitions used in the decision theory [10, 11,12, 30, 31]. It is also observed in several research areas that the experience or the Level of Expertise (LoE) is an important factor to make decisions [32,33,34]. It is found that there is no significant physical (i.e., optometric test) difference of performance between expert and novice decision-makers. The expert group's superiority on the perceptual recall and recognition tasks was consistent with a deeper level of encoding for structured (meaningful) material [14]. It is observed that the expert acquires anticipatory skills to circumvent general limits on reaction time, and distinctive memory skills allow a domain-specific expansion of working memory capacity to support planning, reasoning, and evaluation [15]. It is seen for the medical images that relative to novices, expert cardiologists demonstrated shorter and less variable review times [16]. Thus, the variations in supporting document reading have a deep impact in decision making . This kind of documents are often used in evidence-based health care policymaking [17]. Current hopes for appropriate health policymaking are pinned on rigorous 'systematic reviews' of scientific reports, which attempt to synthesize the entirety of evidence on existing interventions, description of current practices, or prognosis of future states [18]. The structure of the document or the report plays an important role in this. It should contain at least some supports for meta-analysis,

enough evidence for the assessment of the study method and summary of reviews and results to facilitate the evidence-informed policymaking [19]. A generic scientific document structure also supports the over-mentioned document structure for a standard scientific study. Through the studies of generic scientific document structure, it is found that most scientific articles are sequentially structured along the text type-specific categories: problem, evidence, answers. The introduction, background, rationale fall under the category of problem. The method, data collection description and data analysis fall under the category of evidence. The result, interpretation and conclusion fall under the category of answer [20]. This idea of evidence-based health policymaking also currently leads to the data-centric policymaking. In data-centric policymaking it focuses more into the context aware and user-centric policies using recent technologies like sensor data processing [21]. Although it is barely seen in health policymaking, the sensor-based technologies like eye trackers are already used in several other areas of decision making, as it is mentioned in (Ericsson et al, 1996; Brunyé et al 2019[15,16]); in these cases, the participants use a supporting document to decide. Those studies were done to observe the differences between experts and non-experts. Only a few other studies, for example, in the field of Food labeling and purchase decision , communicate about the relationship between the reading behavioral pattern of an individual and the decision taken by the same individual. There are two broad categories of studies of reading behavior using eye trackers: 1. Informational search: reading a document to find information to extract; in this case there is a strong role of human visual search to extract data of related fields and/or to search information in the images [22,23,24]. 2. No informational search, only to acquire supporting information for decision-making: Reading document to have supporting information to take a decision; in this case there is no possible role of human visual search, the participant achieves a higher-level understanding of the whole scenario, that facilitates the decision-making, but no answer is given inside the text [25, 26]. Till date, there are more studies for the first area than the second one, though there are several decision-making tasks where the users do not directly use the data from the given document for their decision-making. This is may be because of the feature extraction constraint in eye tracker. To elaborate on this, we need to know what kinds of feature are used in these analyses. Fixation related features are the main feature in any reading behavior task [42]. A fixation consists of multiple gaze points, fixations have a duration in addition to a spatial (x, y) location and start and end timestamps. The duration of fixation varies between 50 and 600 milliseconds (ms) for our case [39,40,41]. We computed Cognitive Load (CL) as an index of effort exertion, which is measured by the pupil dilation in percentage. Other than fixation, the saccade is another prominent feature if the task involves an exhaustive search for words or any special characteristics in the images. The saccades are faster eye movements than the fixations. Because our task is a task of reading. In our case, the average duration of a saccade is between 20 and 40 ms [39,40,41]. The second group of studies do not involve exhaustive search, so saccade is not used there as a good feature. Besides, there are studies that use visualization of the fixation or eye gaze to study the parafoveal data which is not reflected through numeric values of fixation and saccade [26]. Visualization data also allows qualitative analysis [24]. Finally, the cognitive load feature is useful to understand the level of difficulty of the decision-making task [27].

Data Collection

In this study, we used the data collection from 46 participants (age group from 20 to 54) for our reading and decision-making task, which is described in (Wronski et al 2021) [36]. Among the 46 participants, there were 10 beginner students (1st year bachelors' in interprofessional healthcare or medical students), 29 advanced students (masters' in

health services research and implementation science or medical students with equal to or more than 7th semester of study) and 7 experts, most participants of this expert group were Researchers from the field of health Sciences, some partly involved in policymaking processes. Students received €15 for their participation and professionals were offered a compensation of their travel costs. The participants read a supporting document webpage for around 20 minute to decide on budget policy: prudent (a), lavish (b) and mid-way (c).

Figure 1. The Lab setup for data collection. The brown-line on the table drawn to restrict the distance between user and eye tracker. There were restrictions on back and lateral movement too.

We used Tobii-X1 light device which is a computer monitor-mounted binocular eye tracker for data collection. In an empty, silent, and window-blinds downed room a participant sits with a desktop computer with a Tobii eye tracker. We used Tobii eye tracker software (version 3.4.8) to collect eye-tracker data. This screen-based eye tracker captures gaze data at the speeds of 30 or 60 Hz, and it is designed for fixation-based research. The calibration with five points before data capture was a mandatory act for our task. We used a Windows 7 based eye tracker with the binocular capturing facility. We restricted the participants' movement to keep the same distance from the eye tracker and angle with the eye tracker, through our instruction and vigil (Fig. 1).

How was the application prepared for data collection? We prepared a web-based application as the content of the experiment: Following the same over-mentioned standard guidelines we used a white background and black font colors for text of report; four colors (that is, red, green, violet, and black) are used in the graphs in the report. What material is used for reading? In an HTML page we show an abridged quantitative data report, written in German. This report describes the long-term care situation of people with dementia in a rural district in Baden-Wuerttemberg, Germany. Since our task is related to health policy decision making, the people related to health policymaking or a student of this area can be the best-fitted candidate. The students of health sciences and medicine can also be a good fit because health policymaking is a potential future field of professional activity for these students. Thus, our participants are expected to be aware of all technical terms, they are expected to be able to understand the statistics written in the report, given the educational and/or professional training they received, and are German adults who are fluent in German text reading. We made a summary of the selected part of an already published report due to the genuineness of the task, as this was already written for a specialized audience in health policymaking [43] Fleisch-Kinkaid readability score of this document is 12.3 grades, which states that any German adult after leaving 12 years of study can fluently read this document [35]. Our report consists not only of text but also the graphs. In this work, we do not consider any effective linguistic factors to analyze the text. The report is a well-structured document, it has four basic sections: introduction, method,

result, and discussion. The report consists of graphs and a content page. We collected the eye-tracking data through the Tobii software, then we extracted heatmaps from the data with the webpage background. We used these heatmaps as our primary data. For more details on data collection, we refer to the paper (Wronski et al 2021) [36].

Data Analysis as Priors with Bayesian Inference

Although during data collection in total 20 minutes was allotted for the whole task of reading and decision making, during data analysis we observe that on average 16.4 minutes was taken by all the participants. The average gaze sample of all the participants is 91% and the average weighted gaze sample of all the participants is 88%. The gaze sample percentage is defined as the percent, which is calculated by dividing the number of eye tracking samples with usable gaze data that were correctly identified, by the number of attempts. The weighted gaze sample percentage is defined as the percent, which is calculated by dividing the number of eye tracking samples that were correctly identified, by the number of attempts. This value is weighted based on if both or just one eye was detected in a sample [44]. A low sample percentage reflects many things such as inaccurate configuration, light interference, participant more difficult to track or just a task drawing the participant's attention from the eye tracker track box.

We examine the decision predictability as prior, in the data we collected, likewise it is done in (Morgan et al, 1990) [13]. We can observe given the Levels of Expertise (LoE) what decisions were made by the participants. On the other hand, when we know the decisions made by the participants, can we predict the LoE of the participants? We use Bayesian inference for this analysis. The posterior probability $P(H | E)$ can be computed using Bayes theorem: $P(H | E) = \frac{P(E|H) \cdot P(H)}{P(E)}$, where H stands for hypothesis, whose probability is affected by data, so $P(H)$ are known as prior probability. $P(E | H)$ is known as likelihood whereas, $P(E)$ is marginal likelihood [45].

We aim at observing the relation between the levels of expertise and their decisions. We use Bayesian inference for this purpose. Results of Bayesian analysis using the Levels of Expertise (LoE) of the participant only:

Table. 1 implies to that given the expertise levels of the participants, the advanced level participants have more tendencies to choose option "c", the professional level participants have tendencies not to choose the most expensive option "a", and beginners level participants are slightly more lenient to choose option "c" than the other two options.

Table2 shows the likelihood that a participant has a specific LoE, given the options chosen by the participant. It implies to that if any participant chose the option "a" there is a higher chance that the LoE of the participant is either beginner or advanced. In case a participant chooses the option "c", there is a higher chance that the participant has an advanced LoE. This analysis shows that if the participants choose the option "b", there is equal possibility of that the participant belongs to the any of the three levels of the participants.

Method

As it is mentioned in the Background section, the fixations were found as important feature for a reading behavior study. In this work, we used the visualization of the reading patterns using fixations that would provide us parafoveal information as well. Pure numeric data do not have this information. This helps the human being to qualitatively decide on the reading behavior looking at the heatmap images of reading. On the other hand, it could be also useful as well to use the other features on the top of the visualization of reading patterns.

We used two kinds of evidence: the numeric features like fixation duration to extract the heatmap images of reading of the document, and pupillometric values from eye tracker, which provide the level of difficulty of the participant during the task of decision making.

First, we used the heatmaps as a singular characteristic to achieve the clusters of images. We calculated the Pearson correlation between the images. With these correlation values we computed hierarchical clustering. Then we got the clusters and discussed the results. We achieved the clusters for whole image and for the parts of the images according to the sections of the report. After we achieve the clusters, we need to know the cut-off points of each cluster. We compute the cut-off point of the clusters using the elbow method, which is a common heuristic in mathematical optimization used in determining number of principal components in a dataset [37,38]. It uses explained variation method to acquire the values. In statistics, explained variation measures the proportion to which a mathematical model accounts for the variation (dispersion) of a given set. Here variation is quantified as variance. After we achieve the optimized clusters, we observe the number of fixations for each of the members of the clusters to understand how well the participant read the document. As already noted in background section that fixation occurs during the reading of a document.

A representative image of the whole document with the three colors with average fixation duration in seconds, whose heatmap is displayed, as red: 0.31 - more / yellow: 0.30 - 0.24 / green 0.23-less, is given as Fig. 2.

Figure 2. A representative heatmap of reading where the sections of the reports are marked for explanation.

Finally, we ensembled all features and achieved the prediction results using AdaBoost regressor [28]. An AdaBoost regressor is a meta-estimator that uses AdaBoost boosting algorithm [29]. The AdaBoost regressor begins by fitting a regressor on the original dataset and then fits additional copies of the regressor on the same dataset. In our case a set of ensemble feature included the Level of Expertise (LoE), the pupillometric features (pupil dilation, pupillary response, and pupil dilation) and logit of the pairwise correlation of the heat map images. We add the pupillometric feature (pupil diameter and pupil dilation) as feature to see the effect of cognitive load on the decision making. The AdaBoost regressor can handle many kinds of features, which we also have used in our case, but the simple regressor cannot.

To determine whether there were any patterns in reading activity distinguishing similarity (and dissimilarity) of the heatmap image of number fixations of the eye on the document at the participant level, we performed a hierarchical clustering with Pearson correlation matrix. The correlation was computed using the heatmap images. It computes the correlation coefficient for each pixel between the patches centered on the pixel with the consideration of the standard deviation in the two images of interest.

Result

241

Results of cluster analysis with correlation coefficients between heatmap images

242

243

Figure 3. Dendrogram for all 46 heatmaps of the whole document with the Pearson correlation.

The visualization of this process is given in Fig. 3. In Fig 3, we consider the whole heatmap image found from the reading of each of the 46 participants (in Fig. 3 the participant indices are shown using 0-45 numbers). The shades of color red indicate the strength of the correlation. The darker color shade means stronger (the color code with correlation values is shown in the legends of Fig. 3). Then we apply the elbow method to optimize the number of clusters. For this clustering depicted in Fig. 3, the optimized number of clusters is 4. The optimization is done merging the branches with largest possible distance. Therefore, the cluster of the participants are: C1: 20, 15, 34, 5, 40, C2: 14,35,4,46,19,31,36, 41, 39, 44, 6, 2, 1, 3, 17, 11, 21, 22, 24, 23, 28, 30, 18, 8, 7, 12, 26, 37, 42, 27, 16, 32, 10, 13, C3:25,43,29,33,45, C3_1:9. Because we do not keep a singleton set, we merge C3_1 with C3 as these two are closest; basically, these two sets are branched from the same cluster. Thus, we get three clusters after optimization. In Fig. 3 the clusters are represented in the blue (C1), green (C2) and purple (C3) boxes.

244

245

246

247

248

249

250

251

252

253

254

255

256

Besides, we observe that the average number of fixations in C2 is significantly higher than C1 and C3, whereas the difference of average number of fixations between C1 and C3 is insignificant. That denotes the members of C2 read the document considerably

257

258

259

more than the members of C1 and C3. Now we can consider the joint set of C1 and C3 as the less readers' group and C2 is a more readers' group. Then we observe that 8 members out of the joint group of C1 and C3 took extreme decisions (a: high budget or b: prudent budget), whereas majority member of C2 took the centrist budget decision, i.e., c: midway budget.

In appendix, we repeat the same experiment for the part of the document. When we join the smaller sets of the four parts of the whole document, we find that the members of the smaller set read that part significantly less than the other members and they are more prone to choose extreme decisions.

Result of regression analysis with level of expertise, logit feature from heat map images, and pupillometric features

We conduct the analysis with LoE, heatmap image feature (logit of all correlation value) and the pupillometric features to achieve regression between binary decision: whether it is an extreme decision or not. The regression score of all data from 46 participants is 0.945. In case we use only LoE as feature the probability of prediction is at most 0.80. In case we do not use the LoE feature the performance is significantly down to 50%. In case we do not use pupillometric feature we observe insignificant change of performance. Therefore, LoE is the most important feature to predict the decision, whereas logit of the correlation values of the heatmap images are found as a supportive feature, but in this task pupillometric feature are found not significantly useful. During the analysis, shown in Wronski et al 2021 [36], we also observed that in this task the pupillometric feature is found not significantly determinant of the groups.

We also performed the classification using 20% data as test data and the 80% of data are the training data. We perform this classification with a 5-fold cross-validation strategy. We found the average mean squared error for the prediction is 0.08. The result indicates that LoE is essential feature to predict the decision by a participant, whereas the heatmap images of the fixations on the document by the participants add supporting information to the prediction of decision. The pupillometric features are not found an essential feature in this task.

Discussion

The goal of this work is to understand if it is possible to predict decisions by the participants. To observe the effect of using prior information we performed analysis with LoE of the participants, as LoE has impact on the decisions made. Although it shows interesting result, it is not able to predict with high probabilities. Therefore, we added the reading pattern information of each of the participant using heatmap images through the computation of the correlation matrix between the heatmap images. The overall analysis with clustering shows that members of the minority clusters, who read lesser than the other major cluster, nearly statistically significant choose the extreme option. The heatmap image clustering implies that participants who chose the center option are closely correlated to each other and always belongs to the majority clusters. Therefore, we find that the reading patterns of the participants who took the center option are? similar. Looking at the report sections separately, we saw that the correlation values for introduction and result part are very similar, which may imply to that the participants read these parts of the report similarly. We found from the clustering of the correlation values of the method part that the values differed from each other. It might be due to the reading pattern differences, which may have occurred because some of the participants did not read this part well. The number of fixations calculated from the data of each participants supports this fact. We do not find any

consistent and reasonable pattern for the three expertise groups through the clustering of the correlation values of the heatmaps. Finally, we made an ensemble of the LoE, logit value of the correlation matrix of the heatmap images (a representation of reading patterns), and pupillometric features. As already mentioned in the Method section that, the reasoning behind addition of the pupillometric feature (pupil diameter and pupil dilation) was to see the effect of cognitive load on the decision making. In our task we did not observe the effect of cognitive load, as it was not effectively heavy task for the participants [36]. We observed that the ensemble feature with LoE and logit value of correlation coefficients of the heatmap images show predictability of the decision by a participant.

Conclusion

In this work our main findings are given as follows. We can predict the decision a participant may make after reading the supporting document, using eye tracker data. We show that the heatmap images from eye tracker fixation can be useful as the quantitative measure. Although it is already established as a qualitative measure, it is better to use this feature with other sensitive features, in our case is the LoE. Overall prediction using regression with all ensemble features (level of expertise, logit feature from heatmap and pupillometric features) shows a promising result in the prediction of the decision, whereas only the logit feature from heat map images as a single feature does not have so much prediction power like the ensemble feature set. The accuracy and sensitivity of the prediction becomes better if we use the level of expertise of the participant along with the reading patterns from the eye tracker. Levels of expertise of a human being has significantly good impact on the decision making. Pupillometric features support the prediction well, but as a single feature this bundle of features is not significantly good. This is maybe because in this task we found that that the pupillometric features do not reflect significant difference in the change of the processes. We observe several interesting patterns in this study: 1. the participants those read significantly less than the others are more prone to take extreme decisions for the budget. The extreme decisions are more deterministic in nature, that is either very expensive or very prudent solution 2. The professionals are prone to take either a very prudent or a non-deterministic middle way budget solution 3 Advanced level participants are more prone to take a non-deterministic decision. 4. Beginners' level participants are more prone to take the extreme decisions.

Acknowledgments

We thank our funding body, Klaus Tschira Foundation. We also thank the colleagues of Heidelberg Institute for Theoretical Studies (HITS gGmbH), Department of General Practice and Health Services Research, Heidelberg University Hospital for their kind help during this study.

References

- 1 Staggers, Nancy, and Anthony F. Norcio. "Mental models: concepts for human-computer interaction research." *International Journal of Man-machine studies* 38.4 (1993): 587-605.
- 2 Jonassen, David H., and Philip Henning. "Mental models: Knowledge in the head and knowledge in the world." *Proceedings of the 1996 international conference on*

-
- Learning sciences. International Society of the Learning Sciences, 1996. 352
- 3 Bellenkes, Andrew H., Christopher D. Wickens, and Arthur F. Kramer. "Visual 353
scanning and pilot expertise: the role of attentional flexibility and mental model 354
development." *Aviation, space, and environmental medicine* (1997). 355
- 4 Kolkman, Marinus J., Matthijs Kok, and Anne Van der Veen. "Mental model 356
mapping as a new tool to analyse the use of information in decision-making in 357
integrated water management." *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts 358
A/B/C 30.4-5* (2005): 317-332. 359
- 5 Lavis, John, et al. "Towards systematic reviews that inform health care 360
management and policy-making." *Journal of health services research & policy 361
10.1_suppl* (2005): 35-48. 362
- 6 Fretheim, Atle, Holger J. Schünemann, and Andrew D. Oxman. "Improving the 363
use of research evidence in guideline development: 15. Disseminating and 364
implementing guidelines." *Health Research Policy and Systems 4.1* (2006): 27. 365
- 7 Shanteau, James. "Psychological characteristics and strategies of expert decision 366
makers." *Acta psychologica 68.1-3* (1988): 203-215. 367
- 8 Kahneman, D., Slovic, S. P., Slovic, P., Tversky, A. (Eds.). (1982). *Judgment 368
under uncertainty: Heuristics and biases*. Cambridge university press. 369
- 9 Simon, H. A. (1960). *The Ford distinguished lectures: Vol. 3. The new science of 370
management decision*. Harper Brothers. <https://doi.org/10.1037/13978-000> 371
- 10 Tversky, Amos, and Daniel Kahneman. "Advances in prospect theory: 372
Cumulative representation of uncertainty." *Journal of Risk and uncertainty 5.4 373
(1992): 297-323.* 374
- 11 Camerer, Colin, and Martin Weber. "Recent developments in modeling 375
preferences: Uncertainty and ambiguity." *Journal of risk and uncertainty 5.4 376
(1992): 325-370.* 377
- 12 Knight, Frank Hyneman. *Risk, uncertainty and profit*. Vol. 31. Houghton Mifflin, 378
1921. 379
- 13 Morgan, M. and M. Henrion. "Uncertainty: A Guide to Dealing with Uncertainty 380
in Quantitative Risk and Policy Analysis." (1990). 381
- 14 Abernethy, Bruce, Robert J. Neal, and Paul Koning. "Visual-perceptual and 382
cognitive differences between expert, intermediate, and novice snooker players." 383
Applied cognitive psychology 8.3 (1994): 185-211. 384
- 15 Ericsson, K. Anders, and Andreas C. Lehmann. "Expert and exceptional 385
performance: Evidence of maximal adaptation to task constraints." *Annual review 386
of psychology 47.1* (1996): 273-305. 387
- 16 Brunyé, Tad T., Brahmajee K. Nallamothu, and Joann G. Elmore. "Eye-tracking 388
for assessing medical image interpretation: A pilot feasibility study comparing 389
novice vs expert cardiologists." *Perspectives on medical education 8.2* (2019): 390
65-73. 391
- 17 Dobrow, Mark J., Vivek Goel, and R. E. G. Upshur. "Evidence-based health 392
policy: context and utilisation." *Social science medicine 58.1* (2004): 207-217. 393
-

-
- 18 Pawson, Ray. Evidence-based policy: a realist perspective. sage, 2006 394
- 19 Gray, J. A., and Larry W. Chambers. "Evidence-based healthcare: how to make health policy management decisions." Canadian Medical Association. Journal 395
157.11 (1997): 1598. 396
397
- 20 . Lungen, Harald, et al. "Discourse relations and document structure." Linguistic 398
modeling of information and markup languages. Springer, Dordrecht, 2010. 399
97-123. 400
- 21 Iivari, Marika, et al. "Toward Open Innovation and Data-Driven Health Policy 401
Making." Digital Innovation: Harnessing The Value Of Open Data 4 (2019): 199. 402
- 22 Frey, A., Ionescu, G., Lemaire, B., López-Orozco, F., Baccino, T., Guérin-Dugué, 403
A. (2013). Decision-making in information seeking on texts: an 404
eye-fixation-related potentials investigation. Frontiers in systems neuroscience, 7, 405
39. 406
- 23 Kundel, H. L., Nodine, C. F., Carmody, D. (1978). Visual scanning, pattern 407
recognition and decision-making in pulmonary nodule detection. Investigative 408
radiology, 13(3), 175-181. 409
- 24 Vila, J., Gomez, Y. (2016). Extracting business information from graphs: An eye 410
tracking experiment. Journal of Business Research, 69(5), 1741-1746. 411
- 25 Orquin, Jacob L., and Simone Mueller Loose. "Attention and choice: A review on 412
eye movements in decision making." Acta psychologica 144.1 (2013): 190-206. 413
- 26 Kim, S. H., Dong, Z., Xian, H., Upatising, B., Yi, J. S. (2012). Does an eye 414
tracker tell the truth about visualizations?: Findings while investigating 415
visualizations for decision making. IEEE Transactions on Visualization and 416
Computer Graphics, 18(12), 2421-2430. 417
- 27 Wang, Q., Yang, S., Liu, M., Cao, Z., Ma, Q. (2014). An eye-tracking study of 418
website complexity from cognitive load perspective. Decision support systems, 62, 419
1-10. 420
- 28 Drucker, Harris. "Improving regressors using boosting techniques." In ICML, vol. 421
97, pp. 107-115. 1997. 422
- 29 Freund, Yoav, and Robert E. Schapire. "A decision-theoretic generalization of 423
on-line learning and an application to boosting." Journal of computer and system 424
sciences 55.1 (1997): 119-139. 425
- 30 Ellsberg, Daniel. "Risk, ambiguity, and the Savage axioms." The quarterly journal 426
of economics (1961): 643-669. 427
- 31 Sen, Amartya. Collective choice and social welfare. Harvard University Press, 428
2017. 429
- 32 Herbig, Britta, and Andreas Glöckner. "Experts and decision making: First steps 430
towards a unifying theory of decision making in novices, intermediates and 431
experts." MPI Collective Goods Preprint 2009/2 (2009). 432
- 33 Salas, Eduardo, Michael A. Rosen, and Deborah DiazGranados. "Expertise-based 433
intuition and decision making in organizations." Journal of management 36.4 434
(2010): 941-973. 435

-
- 34 Campitelli, Guillermo, and Fernand Gobet. "Herbert Simon's decision-making approach: Investigation of cognitive processes in experts." *Review of General Psychology* 14.4 (2010): 354-364. 436
437
438
- 35 Flesch, Rudolf. "Flesch-Kincaid readability test." Retrieved October 26.3 (2007): 2007. 439
440
- 36 Wronski, Pamela, et al. "Use of a quantitative data report in a hypothetical decision scenario for health policymaking: a computer-assisted laboratory study." *BMC medical informatics and decision making* 21.1 (2021): 1-14. 441
442
443
- 37 Goutte, Cyril, et al. "On clustering fMRI time series." *NeuroImage* 9.3 (1999): 298-310. 444
445
- 38 Satopaa, Ville, et al. "Finding a" kneedle" in a haystack: Detecting knee points in system behavior." 2011 31st international conference on distributed computing systems workshops. IEEE, 2011. 446
447
448
- 39 Hessels, Roy S., et al. "Is the eye-movement field confused about fixations and saccades? A survey among 124 researchers." *Royal Society open science* 5.8 (2018): 180502. 449
450
451
- 40 Kenneth Holmqvist, Marcus Nyström, Richard Andersson, Richard Dewhurst, Halszka Jarodzka, and Joost Van de Weijer. 2011. *Eye tracking: A comprehensive guide to methods and measures*. OUP Oxford. 452
453
454
- 41 Andrew T Duchowski. 2017. *Eye tracking methodology: Theory and practice*. Springer. 455
456
- 42 Hollenstein, Nora, et al. "ZuCo, a simultaneous EEG and eye-tracking resource for natural sentence reading." *Scientific data* 5.1 (2018): 1-13. 457
458
- 43 Ministry of Social and Integration, Modellprojekt Sektorenübergreifende Versorgung - Abschlussbericht. <https://www.gesundheitsdialog-bw.de/modellprojekt>. Baden-Wuerttemberg, Germany (2018) 459
460
461
- 44 Tobii Technology AB. User's Manual: Tobii X2-60 Eye Tracker version 1.0.3 <https://www.tobiipro.com/siteassets/tobii-pro/user-manuals/tobii-pro-x2-60-eye-tracker-user-manual.pdf?v=1.0.3> (2014) 462
463
464
- 45 Bickel, Peter J., and Kjell A. Doksum. *Mathematical statistics: basic ideas and selected topics, volumes I-II package*. CRC Press, 2015. 465
466
- 46 Ghosh, S.; Wronski, P.; Koetsenruijter, J.; Mueller, W.; Wensing, M.; 2021; Watching people decide: decision prediction using heatmaps of reading of a decision-support document *Journal of Vision* September 2021, Vol.21, 2631. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1167/jov.21.9.2631> 467
468
469
470